

The Fidelity Ladder

Agentic Monte-Carlo Playtesting for Tabletop-RPG Encounter Calibration
An experience report

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June 2026

Abstract

Balancing a tabletop role-playing game (TTRPG) combat encounter increasingly relies on an *abstract* Monte-Carlo simulator: thousands of dice rolls under a scripted policy, read off as a party win rate. We estimate one level-9 *Level Up: Advanced 5E* boss fight at four rising levels of *difficulty-estimation fidelity*: (i) the static Challenge-Rating / encounter-XP budget; (ii) an abstract, positionless Monte-Carlo model with scripted “competence-band” policies; (iii) an *agentic* simulation in which each player character is driven by a large-language-model (LLM) policy on a 2D grid, coordinating with allies, while a deterministic engine resolves all dice; and (iv) a human playtest. Our central observation: raising fidelity does not merely shift the difficulty *level*, it *re-ranks* party compositions. Holding the boss fixed, the positionless model’s confident ordering is overturned — the composition it rates third (an archer trio, 24%) the agentic model rates at 70% (tied for second), and that trio won at the table — because low-fidelity models cannot credit value that is positional. We use the agentic tier to calibrate the boss along two axes, lethality and table-time, to a designer target; the final design produced a clutch table win (two of three characters down, one at 10 HP), confirming the estimate and surfacing a further mechanism the simulation under-modeled. We claim no novelty for the agentic architecture, the balancing loop, or the fidelity-hierarchy idea — each is cited prior art. The contribution is the conjunction: a concrete four-tier instantiation for TTRPG encounter design, a measurement of how far and in which direction estimates move between tiers, and a reusable open artifact.

1 Introduction

A game master (GM) preparing a one-shot wants one thing the rulebook cannot give: *will this fight be hard but winnable, and will it finish in the time we have?* The official answer in Dungeons & Dragons-family systems is the Challenge Rating (CR) budget, a coarse additive heuristic widely known to mispredict actual outcomes. Hobbyist designers have long supplemented it with abstract Monte-Carlo simulators that pit party against monsters thousands of times and report a win rate (BattleCast / community, 2020–; Cavender, 2021). These models are cheap and useful, but they share two simplifications: the combatants follow a *scripted* decision policy, and combat is *positionless* (an HP-versus-HP exchange with, at most, random target selection). The CR budget and the abstract Monte-Carlo simulator are, respectively, the first and second rungs of a *fidelity ladder* of difficulty estimators that we make explicit in Section 6: CR is a static analytic guess; the Monte-Carlo simulator improves on it by actually rolling the fight; the agentic simulator improves further by adding positioning and coordination; and the human table sits on top.

This report grew out of an actual table. We built a five-encounter gauntlet, balanced it with an abstract Monte-Carlo model to a target competent-play win rate, and then — because the abstract model ignores exactly the things a real party exploits — re-estimated the climactic boss

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fight with *LLM agents* playing each PC on a 2D grid, coordinating via messages, over the same deterministic ruleset. The two estimators disagreed, and not by a constant offset: they *re-ordered* which party compositions were strong. We treat that disagreement as the object of study.

What we claim, and what we do not. We do *not* claim novelty for: agentic LLM simulation of D&D combat (this exists, Zeng et al., 2025); the closed-loop use of repeated agent simulation to balance a game (this exists, Zeng et al., 2026; Romeo and Bagdanov, 2025; Shyne and Cooper, 2024); or the concept of an ordered hierarchy of model fidelity (this is a load-bearing idea in modeling-and-simulation verification and validation, Oberkampff and Trucano, 2002; Peherstorfer et al., 2018; Levi-Soskin et al., 2021). The term *fidelity ladder* is our own didactic label for a known arrangement, not a discovery. Our contribution is the *conjunction* and its empirical reading (Section 2 makes the differentiation precise):

1. An LLM-capable *cooperative-PC* policy over the *same* deterministic TTRPG engine used by the calibration loop, with a 2D grid (movement, reach, opportunity attacks, flanking-grants-advantage), reported as a band over three competence levels rather than a single point.
2. Calibration to a designer-fixed numeric win-rate target by root-finding on a scalar difficulty manifold plus discrete roster search, under a hard *table-time* budget — a second axis most balancing work ignores.
3. The empirical fidelity-ladder reading: *how much* and *in which direction* the difficulty estimate moves from abstract to agentic to human, in this domain, including a composition *re-ranking*.

2 Related work and how this differs

Four recent works sit close enough that a reader will name them first; we cite and differentiate each, then place ourselves.

NTRL (Romeo and Bagdanov, 2025) is the nearest in *loop structure*: a deterministic D&D 5E engine, a heuristically-scripted party, ~ 100 simulations per encounter, and a closed reinforcement-learning loop that uses the *simulated* win rate to adjust difficulty. It differs in that its objective is a composite reward (a balanced win rate $\sim 70\text{--}75\%$ *emerges*; there is no designer-fixed numeric target found by root-finding), it *generates* whole encounters rather than calibrating one boss, its policies are scripted (not LLM), and it has no table-time constraint.

No Player Left Behind (Shyne and Cooper, 2024) is an equally strong scripted precursor: a deterministic D&D engine plus simulated games plus a genetic algorithm optimizing difficulty *and* per-player contribution. It is generative and multi-objective rather than target-seeking on a single win-rate scalar, uses scripted PCs, and has no time budget.

RuleSmith (Zeng et al., 2026) is the nearest in *method*: multi-agent LLMs in self-play over a deterministic engine, with Bayesian optimization driving win rates toward 50%. But its domain is CivMini, a two-faction 4X strategy game, and its objective is *fairness between competing factions*, not a cooperative party against a boss.

Setting the DC (Zeng et al., 2025) is the nearest in *agent role*: LLMs play DM, players, and monsters via function calls over a D&D rules engine, with explicit ally-coordination messaging (flank, focus-fire, peel). But its purpose is to *benchmark LLM-agent capability* on six axes; there is no Monte-Carlo calibration loop and no notion of tuning an encounter to a target.

Adjacent: Xiao and Yang (2024) use LLM agents to *measure* game difficulty in Wordle and Slay the Spire, establishing that agent performance correlates with human-perceived difficulty — but for single-player video games, and explicitly for *relative* ordering, not absolute win-rate prediction. Dayo et al. (2025) place an LLM on the *adversary* side and train DQN player agents; coordinating multiple cooperating PCs is named as future work. Numerous hobbyist Monte-Carlo D&D balancers (BattleCast / community, 2020–; Cavender, 2021) establish that win-rate simulation for D&D is not itself new.

	D&D family	LLM coop. PC policy	determ. engine	MC win/ death rate	closed-loop numeric target	table-time budget	comp. bands
NTRL (Romeo and Bagdanov, 2025)	✓	— (scripted)	✓	✓	~ (emergent)	—	—
No Player Left Behind (Shyne and Cooper, 2024)	✓	— (scripted)	✓	✓	~ (GA, multi-obj.)	—	—
RuleSmith (Zeng et al., 2026)	— (4X)	~ (competing)	✓	✓	✓	—	—
Setting the DC (Zeng et al., 2025)	✓	✓	✓	—	—	—	—
Hobbyist MC (BattleCast / community, 2020-; Cavender, 2021)	✓	— (scripted)	✓	✓	—	—	—
Xiao & Yang (Xiao and Yang, 2024)	— (video)	✓	✓	~ (relative)	—	—	—
This report	✓	✓ [†]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Where this case study sits. No prior work combines all columns. [†]Honest caveat (Section 3.5): the LLM-as-PC policy is demonstrated at the 100-fight grid scale; the 10k-run calibration loop runs *scripted* competence-band policies on the abstract engine. The two axes share the deterministic engine but are not run jointly at 10k scale, for cost reasons.

3 Method: four estimators over one ruleset

The system targets *Level Up: Advanced 5E* (A5E), a tactical 5E variant. All dice and rules are resolved by a single deterministic Python engine; agents (scripted or LLM) only *decide*. We never let a language model roll dice.

3.1 Tier 1 — CR / encounter-XP budget

The lowest rung is the official, off-the-shelf estimate: sum monster XP, apply the encounter multiplier for the number of foes, and compare to the party’s thresholds. It needs no implementation; it is the static baseline the other tiers improve on. For our finale it reads only “Medium-to-Deadly” yet the fight plays beyond Deadly — the gap is reported in Table 3.

3.2 Tier 2 — abstract Monte-Carlo with competence bands

Combatants are HP/AC/attack/condition state. A turn is an action chosen by a *policy*; the engine resolves attacks, saves, conditions (prone, restrained, stunned, frightened, taunted), concentration, and the system’s exertion/maneuver economy. Positioning is abstracted: melee reaches its target, ranged is in range, and positional triggers (sneak-attack enablement, pack tactics) fire with stated probabilities. Crucially, the PC policy is provided at three *competence levels* — naive (random/nearest target, no heal triage), competent (focus-fire on the lowest-HP foe, threshold healing, Bless on the opening round), and optimal (competent plus resource timing held for the boss) — so the simulator reports a *band* rather than a single number. We run $N=10^4$ gauntlets per policy. A calibration harness then (a) bisects a scalar difficulty parameter and (b) enumerates monster rosters to drive the *competent* win rate to a designer target while a turn-count proxy keeps the gauntlet within a 4-hour table budget.

3.3 Tier 3 — agentic grid simulation

The same deterministic engine and stat blocks are lifted onto a 2D grid (5-ft squares, pillars, line-of-sight-lite). Movement is range-limited; leaving an enemy’s reach provokes an opportunity attack; two allies on opposite sides of a target grant flanking advantage (which also enables the rogue’s sneak attack). Each PC’s decision is produced by an LLM policy (we used `deepseek-v4-flash`, the DeepSeek V4 Preview snapshot of 2026-04-24, via API): the model receives a textual board state and its character’s options, posts a short coordination message to a shared party channel, and returns a JSON action (move + action). Enemies are run by a fixed competent AI. The LLM never resolves a rule; invalid or missing outputs fall back to the scripted policy. We run 100 fights of the boss encounter, anchored on the two PCs the human players had pre-chosen and varying the third.

3.4 Tier 4 — human playtest

The calibrated encounter was run once at a real table (three players, level 9, \sim 4 hours).

3.5 An honest note on substrate

The two simulated tiers are demonstrated on *different policy substrates*: the 10^4 -run calibration uses scripted competence bands on the abstract engine; the LLM-agent runs are 100 fights on the grid engine. Running 10^4 LLM-agent gauntlets was cost-prohibitive. We therefore do not claim to have “calibrated the boss against thousands of LLM playthroughs.” We claim an LLM-capable PC policy over *the same* deterministic engine the calibration uses, and a fidelity *comparison* between the abstract and agentic estimators on the identical encounter (Section 5.2).

4 Case study: “The Pit”

The testbed is a gladiatorial gauntlet: three learning waves followed by a boss, for a party of three chosen from six pre-built level-9 characters. CR-budget design (aimed “brutal”) was the starting point. The boss, “The Twins” (Corvo and Cinza), is a hand-tuned pair built from the bestiary’s Assassin: two short-sword attacks, sneak attack, a recharge paralytic (stun), a bloodied frenzy (advantage at half HP), and *legendary actions that activate only when one twin remains* — so killing the first brother makes the survivor more dangerous, concentrating lethality in the endgame. Difficulty is delivered by *resource economy*, not inflated numbers: the learning waves are light, between-wave recovery is granted only before the learning waves (none before the boss), so the party arrives attrited.

5 Results

5.1 Tier 2 calibration

For the calibrated design the abstract model (random trios) returned boss win rates of 10% (naive), 40% (competent), 47% (optimal), at an estimated \sim 222 table-minutes — on target, within budget.

5.2 The re-ranking

Holding the encounter *fixed* (the final rocket-tag boss), we compare the abstract estimator (competent policy, $n=10^4$) against the agentic grid ($n=250$ per composition) for the four anchored compositions Magga + Lucrécia + third (Figure 1). Higher fidelity lifts every estimate, but *unevenly*, and the abstract ranking does not survive. The abstract orders the field Gorza (58) > Sombra (51) > Wrenna (24) > Vex (11) — confident that the archer (Wrenna) and the commander (Vex) sit far below the melee striker (Sombra). The agentic grid reorders this to Gorza (92, [88,94]) > Wrenna (70, [65,76]) \approx Sombra (66, [60,71]) > Vex (53, [47,59]): Wrenna rises 46 points to tie Sombra for second and Vex rises 42, while Sombra rises only 15. The positionless model cannot see the value of a unit that fires from safety or buffs from the back, so it under-rates exactly the positional compositions and over-spreads the ranking — its 40-point bottom spread collapses to 17. The shift is *mechanism-dependent*, not a uniform offset; this is the core observation. With $n=250$ the established claims are Gorza first, Vex last, and the overturning of the abstract’s confident “Sombra \gg Wrenna”; the one order we do *not* assert is the precise Wrenna-vs-Sombra rank, whose 95% intervals overlap.

5.3 Coordination in the agent dialogue

What the abstract tier cannot represent, the agentic tier makes legible: each PC emits a short coordination message per turn (the deterministic engine still resolves every die; the messages are

Figure 1: Same final (rocket-tag) boss, two fidelities, for the party Magga + Lucrécia + a third member, ordered by the abstract estimate. Grey: abstract Monte-Carlo competent win rate ($n=10^4$). Blue: agentic grid win rate ($n=250$, 95% Wilson CI). Higher fidelity lifts every bar but *unevenly*: the agentic estimate for the archer composition (+Wrenna) exceeds that for the melee striker (+Sombra) even though the abstract ranks Sombra far higher — the bars cross. The played trio (+Wrenna) is the sharpest case: the abstract rates it 24% (its third pick), the agentic grid 70% (tied for second), and the human table won.

intent and table-talk, not outcomes). Across 100 chat-logged finale fights the party exchanged 1,182 messages (~ 12 per fight), and their content is dominated by exactly the mechanisms the positionless model has no variables for. Four in five messages name a specific twin to converge on — focus-fire target-calling, present in all 100 fights; “protect the frail” call-outs (the tank stepping between the boss and the healer) appear in 90% of fights and reposition/kite call-outs in 69%. A representative winning exchange:

Lucrécia: Bênção para todos, mantenham-se firmes!
Magga: Protegendo Lucrécia, atacando Gêmeo1.
Wrenna: Foco no Gêmeo1, apoio de longe.
Wrenna: Finalizando Gêmeo1.

In four lines the party stacks a buff, positions the tank to cover the healer, kites the archer, and concentrates fire on one brother — the coordination that produces the 25% \rightarrow 70% gap and that a positionless estimator cannot express. The outcome distributions behind that headline differ in kind, not only degree (Figure 2, $n=250$): the abstract tier wipes the party (all three downed, scored as a TPK) in 75% of runs against 30% for the agentic tier, the agentic fights run longer (mean 5.7 vs. 4.0 rounds), and they tend to end with the boss dead rather than the party. Two caveats keep this honest: the policy code-switches between Portuguese and English ($\sim 90\%/10\%$ of messages), an artifact of the underlying model rather than a finding about play; and because the dialogue is stated intent resolved by the engine, it is a coordination signal, not a ground-truth trace of execution. A naive test of whether losing parties break focus-fire discipline was confounded by fight length — wiped parties die before they ever name the second twin — so we make no such claim.

Magga+Lucrécia+Wrenna, SAME boss: abstract MC (win 25%) vs agentic grid (win 70%, n=250)

Figure 2: Distributions behind the headline for the party that played (Magga + Lucrécia + Wrenna), identical boss: abstract Monte-Carlo ($n=10^4$, 25% win) vs. agentic grid ($n=250$, 70% win). A run in which all three PCs are downed is scored as a TPK (3 deaths): downed \neq dead mid-fight, but a wipe in the lethal boss fight ends the party. The deaths panel’s right bar (3 = TPK) holds 75% of abstract runs against 30% agentic; the agentic fights also run longer (mean 5.7 vs. 4.0 rounds) and end with the boss dead (boss-HP mass at 0) rather than near-full.

5.4 Which tactics actually win

The dialogue shows what the agents *attempt*; to isolate what actually *wins* we ablate one tactic at a time in the deterministic grid engine (greedy scripted policy, $n = 3000$ paired runs per arm on identical seeds) and read the change in party win rate (Table 2). This is a controlled test, unlike a correlational “maneuver-efficiency” tally (win rate when a maneuver is used vs. not), which is badly confounded: in our logs “Magga’s Protection” shows a spurious +15 points (used in 75% of wins but 60% of losses) only because it fires when the party is still grouped and surviving, and the boss “focuses the tank” mostly in fights the party is *losing* (22% win when it happens vs. 97% when it does not) — a symptom, not a tactic. Controlled, two tactics dominate: opening with Bless (−19 points when removed) and focusing fire on one twin before switching (−14). Positional Protection, the correlational “winner,” is causally worth only −3 points. The greedy habit of taunting every turn is even net-*negative* in simulation (+30 points when removed): the engine charges a taunt one of Magga’s two attacks and the twins’ elite recovery clears the control — the same under-pricing of control the human table later overturned (Section 5.6), so we read that row as a property of the simulated policy, not a tabletop prescription. The scripted baseline wins 47.5% here, between the positionless competent band’s 25% and the LLM agents’ 70%.

Tactic removed	Win rate without it	Δ vs. full (47.5%)
Bless (open with the party buff)	28.6%	−18.9
Focus-fire (kill one twin first)	33.2%	−14.3
Protection (tank covers the frail)	44.7%	−2.8
Taunt (Magga redirects the boss)	77.3%	+29.8

Table 2: Causal ablation of party tactics on the grid engine (greedy scripted policy, $n = 3000$ paired runs, same seeds; baseline win rate 47.5%). Δ is the win-rate change when the tactic is disabled — more negative means more essential. Bless and focus-fire are the dominant winning tactics; positional Protection is near-zero (its correlational “+15” was a confound); the taunt row reflects the engine charging a taunt one of Magga’s attacks while the twins clear control, an instance of the simulator under-pricing the control the table found decisive.

Figure 3: Calibrating the second axis. Distribution of rounds-to-win for the high-HP frenzy boss versus the rocket-tag boss (lower HP + lone-survivor legendary actions), both in the agentic tier. The win rate lands at $\sim 70\%$ while the victory length is pulled forward into the table-time budget.

5.5 Calibrating for time, not only lethality

The agentic tier also exposed a *pace* problem the abstract model hid: at an 8-round cap, a third of “losses” were the clock expiring with the party alive and the boss near death — artificial losses. Lengthening the cap removed the timeouts but pushed the win rate well past target (the party simply outlasted the boss); adding the bloodied frenzy restored lethality (64% win) but stretched victories to a median of 7–8 rounds (~ 90 boss-minutes). The fix was *rocket-tag*: cut boss HP and add the lone-survivor legendary actions, landing the win rate at $\sim 70\%$ while pulling victories to a median of 6 rounds and eliminating timeouts (Figure 3). Lethality and time are separate axes; legendary actions buy lethality but not speed, while an HP cut buys speed at the cost of lethality — the combination buys both.

5.6 Tier 4 — the table

The players chose Magga + Lucrécia + Wrenna, the trio the agentic tier rated at 70% win against a 25% abstract-competent estimate for the identical boss (Figure 4). They won, but barely: two of three PCs were downed and the survivor (Wrenna) ended at 10 HP — a clutch win consistent with a 70% (likely-but-not-safe) estimate. The survivor lived because the party used a *taunt* to redirect the boss off its lowest-HP target. This is a mechanism the agentic tier under-priced, for two compounding reasons: each twin’s “elite recovery” clears one control condition on its turn, so a taunt on a single twin buys only the one round of redirection until it recovers; and in our engine the taunt action costs the tank one of her two attacks (Section 5.4), so the greedy policy that taunts every turn traded damage for control the twins shrugged off (Table 2). The table used the taunt differently — timed, on the right twin, at the decisive moment to pull the boss off Wrenna — so well-timed control was worth more than the simulator’s indiscriminate use credited. (These are different epistemic objects: a causal $n=3000$ ablation of *indiscriminate* taunting versus a single, well-timed table use — not a contradiction.) Each tier, in other words, surfaced a mechanism the tier below could not see.

Figure 4: The ladder on the party that actually played (Magga + Lucrécia + Wrenna), same rocket-tag boss. The abstract Monte-Carlo win rate rises across competence bands (naive 3%, competent 25%, optimal 33%) but never leaves the “deadly” zone; the agentic grid estimate is 70%, and the human table won (clutch: two PCs down, survivor at 10 HP). The positionless estimator under-rates this composition $\sim 3\times$.

6 The fidelity ladder

We summarize the pattern as a *fidelity ladder* (our label) of *four* difficulty estimators (Table 3): the static CR / encounter-XP budget (Tier 1), the abstract positionless Monte-Carlo model (Tier 2), the agentic positional model (Tier 3), and the human table (Tier 4). Each rung adds mechanisms invisible to the one below — Tier 1→2 adds dice variance and no-rest attrition; 2→3 adds positioning and coordination; 3→4 adds opponent-specific tactics (e.g. the taunt interaction of Section 5.6) — so a higher rung can *re-rank*, not merely re-scale, difficulty estimates. Tier 1 is the coarsest and the one designers actually use: for our back-to-back finale the CR/XP budget reads only “Medium-to-Deadly” (depending on how the boss’s buffs are credited), badly under-rating burst, no-rest attrition, and the three-PC action-economy disadvantage that the simulated tiers expose. This is an instance of the established idea that where a model places fidelity changes its conclusions (Oberkampf and Trucano, 2002; Peherstorfer et al., 2018); what we add is a concrete four-rung instantiation for TTRPG encounter design and a measurement of how far and in which direction the estimate moves. The practical rule we draw: *calibrate at the highest fidelity you can afford, and always close with a human playtest* — CR is a static first guess, the abstract Monte-Carlo model is a useful but biased simulated pass, the agentic model corrects the composition-dependent bias, and the table still owns the last mechanism.

7 Limitations

This is an experience report, not a controlled study, and its claims are correspondingly modest.

- **$n=1$ at the top rung.** A single playtest is anecdote consistent with the agentic prediction, not validation of it.
- **Substrate split** (Section 3.5): LLM policies were run at 100-fight scale; the 10^4 calibration used scripted policies. The fidelity comparison (Figure 1) is apples-to-apples on the same boss, but the calibration loop itself was not LLM-driven.

Tier	Estimator	Adds over the rung below	Difficulty for the finale (party Magga + Lucrecia + Wrenna)	estimate (party)
1	CR / encounter-XP budget (static)	— (analytic baseline)	“Medium–Deadly”:	the back-to-back pair is \approx 130–156% of the Deadly XP threshold, yet per-encounter labels read only “Medium”. Under-rates burst, no-rest attrition, 3-PC action economy.
2	Abstract Monte Carlo (scripted policy, positionless)	dice variance, no-rest attrition	3% / 25% / 33% win (naive / competent / optimal)	
3	Agentic grid (LLM PC policies, positioning, coordination)	positioning, coordination, focus-fire	70% win	
4	Human playtest	opponent-specific tactics (a taunt the sim under-modeled)	1/1 win, clutch: two PCs down, survivor at 10 HP	

Table 3: The fidelity ladder instantiated on the finale, for the party that actually played. The difficulty estimate climbs from “deadly” (Tiers 1–2) to “winnable” (Tier 3) and matches the table (Tier 4); each rung adds mechanisms invisible to the one below. CR is the static baseline the simulated tiers improve on — not a separate concern.

- **Absolute vs. relative difficulty.** The only published validation of LLM-agents-as-difficulty-proxies (Xiao and Yang, 2024) supports *relative* ordering, not the *absolute* win/death rates a calibration target needs. Our absolute numbers are unvalidated assumptions.
- **Samples and a perishable gap.** The re-ranking rests on $n=250$ fights per composition (Figure 1, 95% Wilson CIs $\pm \sim 6$ points): Gorza-first, Vex-last, and the overturning of the abstract’s confident “Sombra \gg Wrenna” are established, but the precise Wrenna-vs-Sombra order is a statistical tie. Fallback to the scripted policy was $\sim 3\%$ in the $n=250$ runs behind the figures (a retry-with-backoff wrapper); the 100-fight chat-logged run used for the coordination analysis (Section 5.3) predates the wrapper at $\sim 15\%$. The nearest neighbors are months old — an exact precedent could appear at any time, and the Zeng et al. (2025) group already holds most of the architecture.
- **Direction is not guaranteed.** We observed the abstract model over-crediting positionless-fragile units; with poorly-positioned scripted enemies the bias could run the other way. We measured one encounter, not a distribution of them.

8 Conclusion

Abstract Monte-Carlo balancing answers “is this encounter winnable?” but, lacking positioning and coordination, it answers the composition question wrongly — it re-ranks under higher fidelity. An agentic tier, with LLM policies on a grid over a deterministic engine, recovers the composition-dependent structure cheaply enough to use in design, and a human playtest still adds a rung. We offer the concrete instantiation, the honest measurement of the shift, and an open artifact, so that game developers can run the same ladder on their own encounters.

Appendix: The party roster

The six pre-built level-9 characters use *Level Up: Advanced 5E* (A5E) classes. Two players locked the tank (Magga) and the healer (Lucrecia); the third slot was varied across the other four (the

compositions of Figure 1). The signature abilities listed are the ones the paper’s mechanics turn on.

Character	Class	AC/HP	Role	Signature ability
Magga	Fighter	20/103	Front-line tank	<i>Protection</i> : disadvantage on one attack/round against an adjacent ally; can <i>taunt</i> a foe.
Lucrécia	Herald	20/74	Healer / support	<i>Bless</i> (+1d4 to allies’ attacks and saves), <i>Lay on Hands</i> , <i>Aura of Light</i> (auto-stabilizes the dying), <i>Divine Smite</i> .
Gorza	Berserker	16/100	Melee bruiser	<i>Rage</i> : resists physical damage; heavy two-handed hits.
Wrenna	Ranger	17/74	Ranged archer	<i>Hunter’s Mark</i> (+1d6); fragile, fights at range (melee adjacency gives her disadvantage, so she kites).
Sombra	Rogue	17/64	Melee skirmisher	<i>Sneak Attack</i> (+6d8, only with advantage or a flanking ally), <i>Uncanny Dodge</i> (halves one hit/round).
Vex	Marshal	18/74	Commander / support	Grants allies extra attacks and bonus dice; <i>Rallying Surge</i> (heal).

Artifact. The simulator (abstract engine, competence-band policies, grid arena, LLM-policy adapter), the calibration harness, and the reproduction scripts are available at <https://github.com/caiocgomes/fidelity-ladder> (commit 989b185) and released under the MIT license. The release is archived on Zenodo for a citable DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20815249>.

Acknowledgments

Thanks to the players of the first table — Victor Caparica, Norbert Caparica, and Pedro Henrique Laureano — whose playthrough produced the human-tier data point, including the taunt tactic that the simulation had under-modeled. The simulation code was developed with the assistance of Anthropic’s Claude Code.

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